

MODERNIZATION OF THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT SYSTEM OF FUTURE TEACHERS AS A SOCIAL NEED

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Abstract. *The article also introduces the PBL-5 approach and the 4 "K" technology as tools for enhancing education in the 21st century. It concludes by emphasizing the need for continuous education reform and adaptation to contemporary demands.*

Keywords: *education as development driver, teacher professional skills, information age impact, 21st century education trends, pbl-5 approach, 4 "k" technology*

Today, consistent reforms and renewal processes are being carried out in all spheres in our country, and a worthy foundation is being laid for a new renaissance - the Third Renaissance. In the new concept of education until 2030 adopted by international organizations and developed countries, it is defined as "Education is the main driving force of development and an important activity leading to the goals of sustainable development".

It should be noted that all over the world special attention is paid to the issue of improving the professional skills of teachers at various stages of their professional activity. As an example of the first research conducted in the world on this issue, we can cite the "Holmes Group Project" introduced at the Faculty of Education of Harvard University [1]. The first phase of this extensive research was aimed at finding measures to prepare teachers for professional activities and increase their influence in society, called "Teachers of Tomorrow".

In today's information age, as one of the important factors of reforming the education system, great attention is being paid to training teachers for professional activities, including the integration of international cultural, social, economic, and political relations, teaching foreign languages, which are considered the main means of information transfer and communication, and arming them with modern knowledge.

According to statistics, 60 years ago, it took 10 days and 50 dollars to send a 30-page text over 50,000 km. 30 years ago, this effort required 1 hour and 30 dollars. Today, it only takes 3 seconds and 1 cent to do so. This data shows the acceleration of information flow. According to the data, the speed and volume of information in the last 50 years is 1 mln. times increased. In the 70s, human knowledge doubled every 10 years, and at the end of the 90s, human knowledge doubled every year. Today, a modern person can acquire information in a day that a person of the past would receive in a lifetime.

This situation did not bypass the education system. Currently, pedagogues and future teachers are required to have the ability to separate useful information from unnecessary information, quality information from poor quality information, and to be able to consciously analyze information. Instead of the traditional educational paradigm (that is, to convey as much information as possible to the learners in a short period of time), the ideas of the developmental,

scientific-technical and technocratic paradigm are gaining priority. The change in the form of education in educational institutions, the need to work in new conditions and environment creates the need to increase the demand for the professional activity of teachers, increase their functional obligations and expand their professional-communicative skills.

In the context of 21st century education, the following issues are considered as the most important trends [3]:

- Lifelong learning;
- Digitization of education;
- Development of competence of teachers;
- Development of inclusive education [4].

In the modernization of the system of professional competence development of future teachers, it is necessary to introduce 2 new technologies: PBL-5 approach technology and 4 "K" technology.

PBL-5 approach technology content:

- Problem-based learning
- Project-based learning
- Product-based learning
- Process-based learning
- People-based learning

Some scholars consider the PBL-5 approach as a methodology based on constructive, cooperative and contextual activities, as well as increasing interest in learning activities and cultivating group relationships [3]. The PBL-5 approach helps connect theory with practice, develops decision-making skills, increases the level of critical thinking, encourages communication and negotiation skills, and helps assess the level of complexity of the issue. In addition, many studies have proven that the PBL-5 approach creates conditions for students to gain deeper knowledge.

The essence of 4 "K" technology:

- Development of critical thinking skills
- Development of creativity skills
- Development of communication skills
- Cooperation, i.e. developing the ability to work as a team

Let's consider the 4 "K" competencies of the 21st century separately:

In January 2020, at the World Economic Forum in Davos, Switzerland, a list of skills required of professionals in the next 5 years was announced.

These skills train the brain and force a person to realize their strongest inner aspects. This is discussed in detail in the bestseller book "100 Ways to Change Your Life". These skills include all four of the 4 "K" competencies.

1. Critical thinking.

It is such a skill that it imposes a condition of criticism and skepticism on even 100 percent confidence in the existing rule or apparent reality. Yes, it is the critical view that serves for the development of the process. As Albert Einstein said, "Success is very simple: when everyone thinks it's impossible, one brave person comes along, looks at their thinking with doubt, and does it".

2. Creativity.

This is a skill that requires the teacher to be very creative and find a solution to the problem in an unconventional way. All the successful people in the world, from businessmen to artists, from craftsmen to IT specialists, from chefs to teachers, are distinguished by this skill. Creativity means imagining something that is still unclear in an unconventional, unique way.

3. Communicativeness.

In general, humanity has passed through several stages during its evolutionary development: “homo habilis” (man who walks upright), “homo potentis” (man of strength), “homo sapiens” (intelligent man). Many researchers have proposed to call our era “homo loguens”, that is, the speaking man. Because every person is not excluded from the process of transmitting or receiving information, which in turn increases the importance of professional-communicative activity.

4. Cooperation, that is, the ability to work as a team.

In the 21st century, cooperation, that is, mutual cooperation, collaboration and integration, is so intense that it is unlikely that a single person or type of activity can achieve success on its own. As long as you are busy with any type of work, you will certainly cooperate with others. And the ability to establish and manage these partnerships will have a significant impact on your productivity. Teaching activity requires cooperation with students, parents, community, management and others.

In conclusion, it can be said that Uzbekistan is following the path of development that it has chosen to raise the education system to a higher level. We believe that the reforms implemented and implemented in our country in recent years will bear fruit soon. It should also be noted that there is always a need for constant renewal and new reforms in the education system. And it is impossible to say that this process is complete. Therefore, in accordance with the requirements of the times, changes and reforms should be adopted on time and put into successful practice. This movement should be turned into a national movement.

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